
THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353853>

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the role, influence of the media, in particular, the Internet, television, in the upbringing of the younger generation.

Keywords: *young generation, internet, television, upbringing, education.*

The backbone of every society and people is the growing younger generation. The prosperity of the country largely depends on the intelligence, knowledge, aspirations and passion of young people. From the first days of Uzbekistan's independence, taking care of the worthy education of students and young people, their physical, spiritual and moral, ideological education has become one of the priorities of state policy. Also in social life, a new attitude has developed towards the upbringing of children and youth. At the same time, the concept of "culture of information consumption" was introduced into communication in scientific literature, that is, it has become simple to learn about new literature through the Internet, hear music, see pictures of famous people in the cinema and headscarves, read a daily newspaper, conduct conversations with educated people, find a new place of work, use of distance learning technologies.

At the center of all reforms carried out in Uzbekistan today is the human interest. In the XXI century, a period of rapid, globalization began in the life of mankind, more intense than any other period. In the Media (Media), globalization is a "sharp information speed", the phrase "window of the world" is often omitted. Indeed, globalization-the media in the universe are successful in showing its influence on each existing front and even changing its content. This leads to the fact that gross informatization based on high-technologies has a positive or negative impact on the consciousness, consciousness and worldview of a person, as a codified force.

The relevance of the graduate. The role of the media in the formation of ideological immunity to alien ideas and various heresies in youth, as well as the

increasing level of youth interest in the internet, determines the influence of aspects on upbringing and the mental state of adolescents and young people, and the relevance of the topic of finding solutions to problems.

Narrative analysis of scientific research on the topic. The issue of the education of the younger generation and the roller studies of media. Media in these processes were carried out on various aspects of the Social Sciences. In Particular, Dj.Kin, Dj.Bryant, S.Thompson, DC.Merill, E.Denis, A. Mol, K.A.Farfieva, B.Ubaydullaeva In the studies of the media and its influence on social education in human life, opportunities are revealed [1].

V.G.Afanasev, Yu.M.Baturn, G.P.Bakulev, V.M.Berezin, V.M.Scientific research was carried out, which substantiated the importance of Media - TV, Internet, film and video products in the life of members of society, in particular young people.

Based on the results of the study, in which the scientific novelty of the article was carried out, it is proved that the socio-psychological objective and subjective factors of the influence of the media on upbringing.

The purpose of the study is to develop socio-psychological recommendations aimed at reducing the negative impact of the media in education, while maintaining the influence of the media in the education of the younger generation. Television and the internet network were chosen as the object of the study. The study used systematicity, comparative-logical analysis. The empirical source of the study was formed by statistical data, the results of questionnaire surveys.

Human knowledge of the world is the main tool in gaining experience. Nor-Bert Vinner, founder of the science of cybernetics, said of this: "Man takes the universe that beats his face through his organs. Informatization is an expression of the meanings that a person receives from him in the process of adaptation to the world. Real life is all about getting real information, " he said. Today, 8% of the information distributed in the World Media is impartial, while 92% is focused on manipulation [2].

"Manipulation "comes from the Latin word" Manus " - slave. The use of the word in the portable sense gives the meaning of skillfully controlling people as if they were driving machines.

In today's society, where information and the word that form its basis are established, the human mind and psyche are becoming the main victims of manipulation. One of the first books on the manipulation of consciousness belongs to the German sociologist Herbert Franke ("the man under consideration", 1964), who

believes that "manipulation is understood as a mental effect that is carried out in a hidden way, in most it harms its "victims"."

It is worth saying that the generation of the XXI century is more aware of the world with the media than the paths, admonitions, fairy tales, public education of adults. In this form, it is called shun-Day in the "legal framework for the protection of the rights of the child: international templates and national laws: "The media is full and partially reduced the display of pornography, drug abuse and violence-related materials in television and filmography, negative depiction of violence and exploitation, as well as the presentation of personnel-identity of children, women and personal relationships in a form, it is necessary to be encouraged for the fact that the rights is distributed and promoted in the principles of equal competence " A. Mol. The mole came to the conclusion in the book "Sociodynamics of Culture". In our time, knowledge is formed mainly not by the order of the educational system, but by the order of the media." Watching TV orc violence causes the migration of aggressiveness, an increase in the norm of audience sensitivity to violence, the formation of ingratitude karma in the form of their social presence.

Empirical study results.

According to statistics, in the United States, 80% of films with the designation "R", that is, those under the age of 17 are banned from viewing, 70% of prohibited video games, and 100% of music with obscene lyrics are sold to children under the age of 17. On average, children under the USA will have time to see 200,000 cases of violence and 16,000 cases of murder before they reach the age of 18. As a result, getting used to such scenes results in the formation of the illusion that any problem can be solved violently. And seduction is perceived as the norm, that is, the established norm. The violence that is shown on television is even more harmful to young children, if we are not, to those under 8 years of age, because they cannot distinguish between the imaginative world and the real one. Psychologist O.Yu. Drozdova's research showed that 58% of young people repeat the behavior of TV viewers, most of them are heroes of foreign films, and 37.3% of young people are trying to commit illegal actions, imitating telegrams [3].

Television, video actions in commercial shops that represent oppression, seduction, viewing of pictures negatively affect such qualities in Uzbek boys and girls as family, neighborhood, decency, cruelty [4].

APEID is an Austrian scientist who studied and summarized educational reforms, innovations in 28 countries located in the Asian Mint of the world (except

for the former Shuro Republics) R. Maclean argues that this is a generational problem of the 1990s. Because foreign books and television, video programs can negatively affect the values, culture and traditions of the Peoples watching them, interfering with the pace of their national development [5].

Anthony Giddens wrote in his sociology that "If television continues to develop as it is now, the child born today will spend the most time sleeping and in the television box when he is 18 years old." Now the scientist's conclusion has found confirmation.

In particular, the Internet today has become the main source of information and information for young people. This question asked to them and proved. "AColat.uz" in an open survey conducted on the site users "where you will receive the necessary information?" when asked the question, 47% answered "from Internet sites." At the same time, 23% of those surveyed answered "friends, acquaintances", 12% "from TV", 5% "from books on the same topic, from the library", 5% "from my reader", 3% "from my parents". It is worth saying that the majority of Internet users in Uzbekistan are young people. The number of members on social networks is increasing day by day due to the young people. From this, an urgent issue is the protection of young people from the intruders entering the Internet, that is the formation of appropriate immunity in them.

Of course, the Internet or television should not be seen as a factor negatively affecting young people. After all, our observations have shown that young people use the global information network mainly in the maxim of obtaining information. According to the experts, the fact that young people have a lot of information raises their knowledge and worldview.

The animation table, which has compiled an electronic edition of " Best educational Sites " ("Best educational sites"), reflects the changes observed in the internet media in the last ten years. According to him, in 2002, the global network users amounted to a total of 569 million people (9.1% of world population), which today reached 2.27 billion. This means 33% of the world's morality. Ten years ago, people spent 46 minutes for the Internet every day, while at the same time this figure was on average 4 hours. The total number of websites was 3 million in 2002, with 555 million sites listed as of 2012 [6].

In 2013 year according to a study conducted by Z.Akhmedova in Jizzakh, it is known that the majority of young people (52%) believe the information they receive

from the internet, 12% do not believe it, and 28% find false information in it. So the Coupe believes in the Internet data.

Today, most of the major information centers in Jahan operate on the internet. The low level of reliability of information on the internet, their negative impact on the consciousness and spirituality of people is also showed.

Distrust of Internet reports is seen as 13% among Japanese respondents, 25% in Germany, 33% in Sweden, 58% in China, 70% in South Korea. There are an increasing number of materials on the internet that leave behind lies, slander, the spirituality of the individual, T. A. Rahmatullaev said, "The fact that an activity that is inevitable to be punished in Real life can be carried out freely in the virtual world allows it" [7].

Any television gives a person information, information, knowledge. The point is only in what kind of information, information, knowledge he gives. Today, in international terminology, the word "Mediocracy" is used, which means "information society". A person does not live by what he knows, but by what he does not know. Therefore, he is looking for information in order to put an end to this question. Whoever is able to trust a person by delivering information of this content, he has the opportunity to establish control over that human consciousness in a certain sense [8].

Today, the 21st century is the era of globalization and the velvet finding of borders, the age of Information Communication Technologies and the Internet, the age of increasing competition in the world market, of course, there is no way to prove. During this period, it is important for parents in working families, nuclear families to keep their children busy with interesting, useful activities and organize a family library in the family, replenish it, form a family reading.

Family reading is a type of activity that means that a book is read and considered by family members together, being the currently forgotten but most effective form of teaching young people to read, and it is advisable for family reading to continue until students in the family graduate from high school. It is also possible from time to time to return to the tradition of family reading and stand by the fact that each member of the family is then engaged in reading works within his desire as a person with an individual interest [9].

Conclusions:

- In the XXI century, a fierce rapid, globalization process has a significant impact on the upbringing of children. The first information that since human beings

are the main means of knowing the world, gaining experience, the saturation of young people with information in their needs is the main function of the media today;

- youth lifestyle, imagination are formed under the influence of the media;

- the Internet, due to the fact that the media are an important psychological factor, affects the process of television communication. The presence of the image of an "ideal show" or "ideal Internet site or channel" in each subject makes it possible to strive to develop it into a reality on the created show or channel, to compare it with a real perceived TV show or channel is a conflict of regulation of communication;

- most of the information currently distributed in the World Media is focused on manipulation, and the media in particular, the Internet today has become the main source of information and information for young people;

- the media today do not form stable systematic ideas of young people about values. Knowledge of the world is formed by the media with a non-linear nature, and with the participation of the state, political and economic forces mediate behind them. Having studied the position of the media in the upbringing of the younger generation, we can give the following practical suggestions:

- development of psychological functions such as "sorting information", "protection", "fight against" and "control" in information attacks in adolescents, both internal and external, is the main factor in strengthening the ideological immune system in them, and it is necessary to take into account the principle of Service;

- the formation of an ideological element is effectively blurred in a systematic way, taking into account all the factors that determine the formation of an ideological element, in particular, the individual-psychological and axial characteristics of the individual;

- in order to prevent or reduce the negative influence of the media in the upbringing of the younger generation, it is necessary to form a culture of Family Reading. It provides for the consideration of the recommendations in the melody:

- always dividing an example for children in a book reading;

- at certain times in the circle of the family, it is necessary to take turns reading books;

- presentation of a book, referring to the age and character trait of each child, the spiritual-spiritual world;

- a selection of works written in capital letters, written in more colorful pictures on young children, able to reflect the boundaries of his impeccable imagination;

- and for a middle-aged reading child, to recommend works in which the fate of equal heroes is reflected, vivid, fantastic events are depicted, and fun is animated;
- with independent, family-friendly children of older age, is often confused about the reading of books, giving the necessary recommendations (this provides the basis for continuing the tradition of Family reading as a sacred value);
- setting and regular control of the daily and weekly amounts for each book reading;
- to organize a round table in the family on the content of the work read, the character of the characters, the creative approach, the impressions received;
- encourage a reading child who has read on time and on demand;
- to engage in a dialogue with a child who does not express enough heat to a non-fiction teacher, who is unable to complete assignments in his competence, to achieve the development of reading skills in him.

REFERENCES

1. Bryant J., Thompson S. Fundamentals of Media Effects. - Williams, 2004.
2. Keen J. Mass media and Democracy. - M., 1994.
3. Merrill J., Dennis E. Conversations about media. - M.: RAIPC, "Viagrus", 1997.
4. Sociology of the national mentality / text of lectures. Developer M.B.Saliev. - Fergana, 2001. - 131p.
5. Mol A. Sociodynamics of culture: Trans. from fr. / Foreword by B. V. Biryukova. Ed. 3-E. - M.: LKI Publishing House, 2008. - 416 p
6. Mol A. Sociodynamics of culture: Trans. from fr. / Foreword by B. V. Biryukova. Ed. 3-E. - Moscow: LKI Publishing House, 2008.
7. Primav B. Crowd culture-Fayriakhlaki khadisa // contemplation. - 2012. - № 1. -108p.
8. Rasulova Z. Raising children: shortcomings, mistakes, problems and their solution - Tashkent: generation of the new century, 2019. - 304 p.
9. Rahimova K., Abdullaeva A. Psychology of adolescents with difficult upbringing. - Fergana, 2006. - 96 p.
10. Research: how does television affect child education// islaminstitut.com
11. Upbringing: (encyclopedia for parents and coaches) □ / developer M.N. Aminov. - T.: State scientific publication "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan"., 2010. - 406 p.
12. Ubaydullaev B. Traditions and modernity in the upbringing of the younger generation of Uzbeks. - Tashkent, 2010. - 215 p.

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13. Farfieva K.A. The Uzi specificity of the formation of social representations in students under the influence of the media (on the example of television): Psychol. science. name. for level... Author. - Tashkent, 2005.
 14. Chupriy L.V. The negative impact on children of television and the Internet // How. information/children-health/article-36881 negative-impact-on-children-of-television-and-the-internet
 15. Qarshiboeva V. www.uz websites: the combination of educational goal and national cadres // treatments. 5 September 2012.
 16. Karshiboeva V. Audience society: the border between TV and Real life // upbringing. - 2010. 5-th. - 14p.
 17. Karshiboeva. V. Burn by blowing up the TV // enlightenment. 16 November 2012.
 18. Koranov M. National Education. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2007. - 240 p.